

Synthesis and Characterisation of Cobalt-, Nickel-, Copper- and Zinc(II) Complexes of Morin

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Manuscript received 16 October 1995, revised 17 April 1996, accepted 19 June 1996

In this communication we present the isolation of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of morin and their characterisation on the basis of thermal, electronic, ir, ¹H nmr and mass spectral data

Results and Discussion

All the metal complexes behave as non-electrolytes in DMF (~10⁻³ M solution) and do not contain the anion of the metal salt used for their preparation. Elemental analysis data (Table 1) of the complexes indicate 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry. The Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes have normal magnetic moments.

tensity bands at 3 500–3 600 cm⁻¹ indicate the presence of coordinated water molecule. The complexes show additional bands at ~450 and ~420 cm⁻¹ assignable to ν_{M-O} vibrations.

The ¹H nmr spectrum of morin shows five well-defined one-proton signals in the low field at δ 12.618, 12.484, 10.732, 10.125 and 9.796 ppm, assigned^{3,4} respectively to the hydrogen bonded 5-OH and 3-OH, 7-OH, 4'-OH and 2'-OH. The spectrum of the Zn^{II} complex shows only four such signals at δ 12.596, 10.728, 9.886 and 9.924 ppm. This indicates that only one of the hydroxyl protons is replaced by the metal ion during complexation.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MASS SPECTRAL (cm⁻¹) DATA OF THE METAL COMPLEXES OF MORIN (HL)*

Compd	M p °C	μ _{eff} B M	Metal % Found / (Calcd)	m/z
Morin	299	—	—	303, 287, 153, 137, 121, 79
[ZnL ₂ (OH ₂) ₂]	348	—	9.24 (9.29)	703–701, 667, 654, 609, 519, 460, 413, 395, 366
[CuL ₂ (OH ₂) ₂]	360	1.79	9.00 (9.06)	701, 697, 665, 643, 607, 585, 555, 539, 517, 449, 409, 371, 364
[NiL ₂ (OH ₂) ₂]	365	2.96	8.25 (8.43)	696, 660, 658, 629, 595, 555, 496, 465, 433, 409, 385, 355, 341
[CoL ₂ (OH ₂) ₂]	368	4.70	8.31 (8.45)	—

*All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analysis

The ir spectrum of morin (1) is characterised by the presence of an intense band at 1 658 cm⁻¹ (hydrogen bonded carbonyl function) and a broad band at 2 900–3 400 cm⁻¹ (O–H of associated hydroxyl groups)¹. The band at 1 658 cm⁻¹ disappeared and instead a new band appeared at ~1 620 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of all the metal complexes, assigned to metal-bonded carbonyl group². The spectra of complexes show weak band at 3 050 cm⁻¹ due to ν_{C-H} and a comparatively broad band at 3 100–3 400 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of both hydrogen bonded (probably intermolecular) and free hydroxyl groups. The medium in-

The absence of the ligand signal at δ 12.618 ppm in the complex suggests that the 5-OH proton is replaced by the metal ion. The signal at δ 12.596 ppm in the complex is due to the 3-OH group⁴. The upfield shift of the proton is presumably due to its disengagement from the internal hydrogen bonding in the complex. The integrated intensities of the aryl proton signals observed in the range δ 6.158–8.428 ppm of the complex agree well with the [ML₂] stoichiometry.

The FAB mass spectrum of morin shows an intense (P+1)⁺ ions base peak indicative of the stability of the heterocyclic system. The formation of major fragments can be conveniently explained by the retro-Diels-Alder reaction⁵ of the parent ion giving an abundant ring-A fragment at m/z 153 and the less abundant ring-B fragment at m/z 150, and rearrangement of these two fragments to a more stable ion radical of m/z 137 [C₆H₃CO(OH)₂]⁺. The mass spectra of the metal complexes show relatively intense peaks due to [ML₂(OH₂)₂]⁺, [ML₂]⁺ and [ML]⁺ in the range m/z 350–365. The important metal containing fragments with relative intensity greater than 1% are presented in Table 1.

The thermograms of all the complexes show a two-stage decomposition pattern and agree well with the for-

mulation of the complexes. The first stage corresponds to the loss of two water molecules at about 150°. The second stage represents the complete loss of the coordinated morins in a single step. As this conversion occurs within a short range of temperature (3–6°), the kinetic parameters are of no relevance.

In the visible region the Ni^{II} complex exhibited three bands at 24 038, 13 230 and 7 920 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the three spin-allowed transitions of Ni^{II} ion in an octahedral environment. The calculated ligand field parameters such as Dq (792 cm⁻¹), B' (900 cm⁻¹), β (0.853), $\beta\%$ (14.72) and LFSE (27.1 kcal mol⁻¹) suggest an octahedral geometry. The highest energy transition, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ at 17 793 cm⁻¹ of the Co^{II} complex indicates its O_h geometry.

A broad band at 16 665–13 335 cm⁻¹ region along with the room temperature μ_{eff} value of 1.79 B.M indicate a distorted O_h geometry to the Cu^{II} complex.

Experimental

Morin (Sigma) was used as such for preparing metal complexes, and for recording spectra it was recrystallised from hot methanol. The metal complexes were prepared by adding an aqueous solution (10 ml) of the metal(II) acetates

(0.001 mol) to a solution of morin (0.002 mol) in methanol (15 ml). The mixture was then refluxed for ~3 h and cooled to room temperature. The precipitated product was filtered, washed with water and dried under reduced pressure.

Electronic spectra (DMSO, $\sim 10^{-3}$ M) were recorded on a Hitachi 320 spectrophotometer, ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 397 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Varin XL (300 MHz) instrument and FAB mass spectra (using argon) on a JEOL SX 102/DA-6000 spectrometer. Thermograms were obtained from a Delta Series TGA 7 instrument at a heating rate of 15°/min.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the U.G.C., New Delhi, for providing a Junior Research Fellowship to one of them (P.V.), to C.D.R.I., Lucknow, for mass spectra and to R.S.I.C., I.I.T., Bombay, for ¹H nmr spectra.

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